

PROBLEMS OF CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS OF "EDUCATION"

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabi o'qituvchilarining uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlantirishga oid olimlarning tadqiqotlari tahlil etilgan va "Tarbiya" fani o'qituvchilarining uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlantirish muammolari keltirilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: tarbiya, uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlantirish, pedagogik shart, masofaviy ta'lim, mobil texnologiya.

Abstract. This article analyzes the research of scientists on the continuous professional development of teachers of the general secondary school and presents the problems of continuous professional development of the teachers of "Education".

Key words: education, continuous professional development, pedagogical condition, distance education, mobile technology.

In today's globalization, developing new approaches to continuous professional development of school teachers, developing their professional competence remains one of the important issues [1-3]

Researches on these issues in our country, that is, on the theory and practice of continuous professional development of school teachers, by scientists such as A.S.Djurayev, M.T.Jumaniyozova, D.M.Khakimova, A.A.Ibragimov, D.M.Mamatkulov, Sh.Q.Mardonov, A.E.Obidov, D.O'.Karshiyeva conducted.

It was also researched by scientists such as S.K.Berezhnaya, S.G.Yemuzova, L.V.Ivanova, G.V.Kalkova, Z.Z.Serganova, N.Kh.Sirempilova on the issues of improving the qualifications of teachers in the conditions of multi-level education in the Commonwealth of Independent States.

Such studies are also reflected in the scientific and methodological articles of P.A.Orzhekovsky, S. Ye.Mansurova, S.Y. Stepanov, Ye.O. Serkina, Ye.Y.Zimin, A.I. Frolova, D.A. Sukhanov, V.P. Veidt, T.A. Telesheva, Y.M. Markov.

In the works of the above-mentioned scientists, the theory and practice of continuous professional development of general secondary school teachers, the technology of developing teacher's project competence in the process of professional development, the mechanism of modular formation of training content based on professional needs, in the process of continuous professional

development technologies for the development of the innovative potential of school teachers are focused on the method of using distance education in improving the qualifications of school teachers, but in their research, the "Education" science teachers continuous professional development is not paid attention to. Therefore, the ongoing research, i.e. the continuous professional development of teachers of "Education" is one of the urgent problems.

Because in the current socio-cultural situation, unpleasant phenomena such as alcoholism and drug addiction, moral decline, and the rise of criminality are increasing. The number of schoolchildren is increasing every year, and there is a sharp increase in behavioral characteristics such as aggression, indiscipline, conflict, lack of self-control. Because in the current socio-cultural situation, such unpleasant phenomena as alcoholism and drug addiction, spiritual decline, rejuvenation of crime are increasing. In this, the number of schoolchildren increases every year, and there is a sharp increase in behavioral characteristics such as aggression, indiscipline, conflict, lack of self-control [4].

Also, in the conditions of fundamental changes that cover all aspects of society's life, along with positive changes that encourage the improvement of many areas of human activity, negative trends are also increasing: socio-economic instability, unemployment, decrease in the standard of living of the population; socio-psychological disorientation and maladaptation of people, a sharp decrease in the demand for universal moral and spiritual values, a severe criminal situation, weakening of the activities of social institutions designed to engage in education, etc.

Such alarming trends require an urgent review and improvement of the social preventive activities of the state and society, all social institutions [4]. Retraining of school teachers, including teachers of "Education" and their continuous professional development, is of great importance in this regard.

However, despite the fact that the normative documents on the teaching of education in general secondary schools are set as a priority task, attention to it cannot be said to be at the required level. As an example of these, the experience of teachers teaching "Education" is not at the level of students and some problems in continuous professional development. Therefore, today, the development of scientifically based methodology for the continuous professional development of teachers of "Education" remains one of the important issues.

The ongoing research is also focused on this issue, that is, the development of technologies for continuous professional development of teachers of "Pedagogy" in the context of globalization education. For this, it was

concluded that it is necessary to analyze the state of continuous professional development of teachers of "Education" in pedagogical skill centers, and observation work was carried out. Interviews and questionnaires were conducted with teachers of pedagogical skill centers and course participants during the observation work.

In addition, several trainings of the course participants of pedagogical skill centers were observed to determine the level of knowledge in the field of "Education". We were sure that in the observed pedagogical skill centers, teachers conduct training with the help of advanced pedagogical technologies and digital tools. But it turned out that the teachers of these pedagogical skill centers could not increase the interest of the course participants ("Education" subject teachers).

In our opinion, the reasons for the emergence of such problems in the continuous professional development of "Education" teachers in pedagogical skill centers can be cited as follows: insufficient scientific and methodical resources related to the continuous professional development of "Education" teachers; It is necessary to improve the pedagogical conditions for the continuous professional development of the teachers of the "Education" subject; It is necessary to improve the mechanisms of using distance learning systems in the continuous professional development of teachers of the subject "Education"; insufficient attention is paid to the organization of training based on the integration of digital educational technologies and problem-based educational technologies in pedagogical skill centers; The existence of the introduction of scientifically based mobile education in the process of continuous professional development of teachers of the subject of education.

In short, on the basis of solving the above-mentioned problems, it is possible to improve the mechanisms of continuous professional development of "Education" teachers.

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